

On the Benefits of Self-Adaptive Interpolation in Coarse Mesh Rebalancing for Nodal Diffusion Computations

R. van Geemert* ^{1,*}

¹Framatome GmbH, Erlangen, Germany

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803225

ABSTRACT

Coarse Mesh Rebalancing (CMR) is a well-established methodology in computational reactor physics. Among others, it enables a significant acceleration in the numerical convergence of 3D full-core nodal steady-state and transient computations. For enabling a further CMR efficiency upgrade, a novel self-adaptive interpolation approach has been developed. Through its integration in the automated computation of the relevant restriction and prolongation operators, a transformed rebalancing equation emerges. The latter features an improved projection of the influential couplings between the different parts of the reactor core. This approach has been verified to be compatible with the use of the established semi-analytical Nodal Expansion Method (NEM-SA) in both steady-state and transient nodal diffusion. For the overall multi-group nodal flux iterative solution process (and also for the enveloping multi-physics-coupled solution processes), this has enabled an additional upgrade in CMR efficiency and robustness. This article offers a discussion of the developed method, followed by examples of achieved improvements.

Keywords: Full-core 3D nodal diffusion computations, coarse mesh rebalancing, interpolation, acceleration

1. INTRODUCTION

The ARTEMIS nodal multi-physics reactor code [1] is part of Framatome's ARCADIA Code Suite for LWR core design and transient safety analysis [2]. For enabling optimal quality, dependability and efficiency of ARTEMIS applications for customers, improvement efforts are being pursued continuously. In this context, computational efficiency and robustness are obviously among the most essential simulator properties. In response to new applications and new challenges, the associated state-of-the-art for those properties must periodically be questioned, reconsidered and redesigned. In the nuclear industry, countless numbers of 3D full-core steady-state and transient reactor computations are being pursued every day. With acceptable run times being required, the relevant iterative solution processes must include very effective convergence acceleration mechanisms. Since many years, this functional role is being fulfilled in ARTEMIS by a mature, multi-level implementation of the Coarse Mesh Rebalancing (CMR) methodology. From the applied mathematics perspective, there is a clear similarity with the known multi-grid approach [3] [4] for accelerated solution of fine-mesh partial differential equations. Different in-depth studies [5] [6] have been conducted on why application of coarse mesh rebalancing can enable a very powerful acceleration effect. In the 1980s and 1990s, CMR was integrated in a number of predecessor industrial nodal reactor codes, such as the 3D full-core reactor kinetics code PANBOX [7] and the reactor cycle analysis code PRISM [8]. In the early 2000s, PANBOX and ARTEMIS were extended with adaptive smoothing strategies and preconditioned Krylov subspace methods [9] in their rebalancing routines. As a result, noticeable CPU run time reductions were achieved for steady-state and transient computations pursued with PANBOX and ARTEMIS. Nonetheless, a further upgrade in CMR acceleration effect proved possible, through inclusion of a novel self-adaptive interpolation approach in the coarse mesh projection mechanisms. This is the topic of this article.

*rene.vangeemert@framatome.com

2. COARSE MESH REBALANCING FOR NODAL DIFFUSION COMPUTATIONS

The ARTEMIS-specific coarse mesh rebalancing approach has been described in a previously released publication [9]. A central role is played by the nodal process rate balance equation that determines the nodal fluxes as a function of the interface currents entering and leaving a node. Accordingly, this equation can be used as a basis for restriction to a coarser space-energy mesh. Whereas the derivations are very similar between transient and steady-state nodal diffusion, in this article we will focus on the stationary state, for which the nodal balance equation [9] can be denoted generally as

$$\underbrace{\sum_{Rg}^m \phi_g^m}_{\text{removal}} = \frac{1}{k_{eff}} \chi_g \sum_{g'=1}^G \underbrace{\nu \Sigma_{fg'}^m \phi_{g'}^m}_{\text{production}} + \sum_{g' \neq g}^G \underbrace{\Sigma_{gg'}^m \phi_{g'}^m}_{\text{inscatter}} + \sum_{u=x,y,z} \frac{1}{a_u^m} \left[\underbrace{(j_{gul}^{+m} + j_{gur}^{-m})}_{\text{incurrents}} - \underbrace{(j_{gul}^{-m} + j_{gur}^{+m})}_{\text{outcurrents}} \right] \quad (1)$$

with m: nodal index, g: group index, u: Cartesian axis index, with the a_u^m denoting the nodal mesh dimensions along the Cartesian axes $u(=x,y,z)$, l and r denoting left and right direction, k_{eff} denoting the effective multiplication factor, χ denoting the fission spectrum, with literature-consistent notations for the macroscopic cross-sections (removal as absorption + outscattering, inscattering, production-through-fission), and with the relationship between the nodal outcurrents j_{gul}^{-m} and j_{gur}^{+m} , fluxes ϕ_g^m and incurrents j_{gul}^{+m} and j_{gur}^{-m} defined in [10] (cf. Fig.1). For steady-state computations on self-sustaining reactors, effectively a *large sparse eigensystem* is solved (with usually a criticality search for enforcing $k_{eff} = 1$). The NEM-methodology supplies numerically convenient relationships between interface-averaged outcurrents versus nodal fluxes and interface-averaged in-currents [10]. Combined with Eq.(1), these provide a tractable basis for the iterative solution of the whole-core nodal fluxes and interface currents. Depending on the order of the applied intranodal expansion, higher-order expansion coefficients are co-solved through weighted residual (WR) and transverse leakage (TL) procedures [10] [11]. The derivation can be done by integration over volume and energy (thereby eliminating spectral scattering terms that systematically add up to zero). In case of keeping the same spatial mesh, this leads to the following projected equation, from which the nodal rebalance driving factors d_m (cf. Fig.2), the interface current rebalancing driving factors $\tilde{d}^{m \leftarrow m'}$ and the eigenvalue k_{eff} can be solved iteratively:

$$\left[A_m - \frac{1}{k_{eff}} F_m \right] d_m + \sum_{m'(m)} J^{m' \leftarrow m} \tilde{d}^{m' \leftarrow m} = \sum_{m'(m)} J^{m \leftarrow m'} \tilde{d}^{m \leftarrow m'} \quad (2)$$

in which $\sum_{m'(m)}$ indicates a sum over all neighbor nodes m' that are directly adjacent to node m. The rebalancing operators are defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} A_m &= V_m \sum_{g=1} \Sigma_{ag}^m \phi_g^m \\ F_m &= V_m \sum_{g=1} \nu \Sigma_{fg}^m \phi_g^m \\ J^{m \leftarrow m'} &= \frac{V_m}{a_{u(mm')}} \sum_{g=1} j_g^{m \leftarrow m'} \\ J^{m' \leftarrow m} &= \frac{V_m}{a_{u(m'm)}} \sum_{g=1} j_g^{m' \leftarrow m} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

in which V_m denotes the volume of node m. Prior to the development described in this article, the approximation $\tilde{d}^{m \leftarrow m'} = d_m$ has always been the default. This yields the obvious advantage of thereby acquiring a more simple equation that features a low dimension for its solution:

$$\left[A_m + \sum_{m'(m)} J_{m' \leftarrow m} - \frac{1}{k_{eff}} F_m \right] d_m = \sum_{m'(m)} J^{m \leftarrow m'} d_{m'} \quad (4)$$

Figure 1. NEM-relationship between cross-sections, incurrents, fluxes and outcurrents

Upon having been solved iteratively from Eq.(4), the obtained driving factors d_m can be applied for pushing the convergence of the nodal fluxes and currents. The computational cost of pursuing a single iteration step for Eq.(4) is very low compared to one whole-core multi-group nodal diffusion sweep (which feature complex interface current equations, WR-terms, TL-terms, exponentials and several inner iteration processes). Following each rebalancing operation, before doing the next whole-core diffusion sweep, the multi-group fluxes and outcurrents are multiplied correctively with the iteratively obtained driving factors (with the prior default being $d^{m' \leftarrow m} = d_m$):

$$\mathbf{P} [d_m] : \begin{pmatrix} \phi_g^m \\ j_g^{m' \leftarrow m} \end{pmatrix} \longrightarrow \begin{pmatrix} d_m \phi_g^m \\ \tilde{d}^{m' \leftarrow m} j_g^{m' \leftarrow m} \end{pmatrix} \quad \forall g, m, m'(m) \quad (5)$$

Upon final convergence of the nodal diffusion solution, all d_m will converge to the value 1.

Figure 2. Two-dimensional illustration of the association of driving factors with nodal volumes

The spatial grid in the coarsened space-energy mesh is usually the same as the spatial grid for the nodal diffusion iterations. Accordingly, it can be worthwhile to also project this equation to a further coarsened spatial grid. This approach leads to a *multi-level V-cycle design* [9]. In ARTEMIS, the number of applied rebalancing levels is determined through an automated procedure. For most of the relevant core computations, a hierarchy of up to six coarse mesh levels is common.

3. A SELF-ADAPTIVE INTERPOLATION APPROACH FOR DRIVING FACTORS IN COARSE MESH REBALANCING

In its nodal diffusion steady-state and transient computations, the ARTEMIS reactor code includes the standardized usage of the semi-analytical Nodal Expansion Method (NEM-SA) [11]. This features the co-solution of nodal interface currents based on the so-called interface current equations. Their combination with the nodal process rate balance equation (Eq.(1)), the Weighted Residual (WR) equations, and the Transverse Leakage (TL) equations, gives rise to the total set of equations to be solved. For each individual node, beyond the multi-group nodal fluxes and interface currents, several types of expansion coefficients are to be co-solved. This means that several implicit terms, whose determination requires separate embedded iteration sub-processes, appear additionally. For any modeled reactor core, the relevant NEM operators are determined mainly by the nodal mesh dimensions and by the cross-sections as determined by the fuel composition distribution, burnup, operational conditions, feedback processes, control rod insertions, boron concentration, and so on. For each core flux computation, the numerical flux convergence behavior is determined by the iterative solution setup for this whole set of equations and sub-equations, of which Eq.(1) is actually a small (though very central) part. When using Eq.(1) as restriction basis, for optimizing the CMR acceleration effect it makes sense to include additional node-to-node coupling physics information that is consistent with the interface current equations. A suitable approach for that is to include a *driving factor interpolation* to the coarse mesh projections, by defining interface-dependent driving factors. Each of those can be constructed as a weighted sum of nodal (interface-independent) driving factors: the one for the concerned node itself, and those associated with its closest neighbors along the three Cartesian axes. The analytical expressions for these weighted sums are entered into the derivations of the rebalancing equation, as interface-dependent driving factors associated with the interface current values to be projected. The thereby re-arranged rebalancing equation then includes the node-to-node coupling physics dictated by the interface current equations in its algebraically re-arranged operators. Simultaneously, this transformed rebalancing equation does preserve the advantage of having to iteratively solve only the nodal driving factors d_m . In this manner, the low computational cost of rebalancing iterations is preserved. Another attractive property is that the applied weighting factors do not necessarily need to be exactly consistent with the more complex interface current equations as commensurate with NEM-SA (with WR and TL terms added. etc). Instead, they can be reasonably approximated by analytically computable coefficients that can be derived from (a re-arranged formulation of) a far more simple, lowest-order polynomial NEM formulation. The NEM-M0 formulation [10], which is the easiest, most compact interface current equation formulation (without WR or TL terms included) was adopted for that purpose. Accordingly, some effort has been pursued for deriving the required rearranged formulation of the NEM-M0 equations. In order to start illustrating this approach, let's recall the NEM-M0 formulation [10] for the interface current equations:

$$\begin{aligned} j_{gul}^{-m} &= c_{1gu}^m \phi_g^m + c_{2gu}^m j_{gul}^{+m} + c_{3gu}^m j_{gur}^{-m} \\ j_{gur}^{+m} &= c_{1gu}^m \phi_g^m + c_{3gu}^m j_{gul}^{+m} + c_{2gu}^m j_{gur}^{-m} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

For each node, the NEM-coefficients c_{igu}^m are determined primarily by the group-wise nodal macroscopic neutron transport cross-sections and by the local nodal mesh dimensions a_u^m . Most of the nodal computations are pursued with use of only two condensed energy groups. Combined with Eq.(1), Eq.(6) constitutes the entire set of equations to be solved in the NEM-M0 formulation. Yet numerically its solution is sufficiently close to that of a state-of-the-art nodal solver for enabling the extraction of the prior-mentioned well-suitable interpolation weight factors. The latter can be done by transforming Eq.(6) towards a re-arranged formulation from where expressions for those interpolation weight factors can be extracted. The mathematical derivation follows from successively inserting the NEM-M0 outcurrent equations for the incurrents. The latter are nothing but outcurrents that originate from those neighboring nodes. Doing this repeatedly (and applying some tiring but otherwise straightforward algebraic manipulations) enables to establish a transformed (and equivalent, fully exact) set of NEM-M0

interface current equations that (with l denoting left and r denoting right) can be denoted as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 j_{gul}^{-m} = & \alpha_{0lgu}^m \phi_g^m + \alpha_{gull}^m \phi_g^{m_l(m_l, u)} + \alpha_{gulr}^m \phi_g^{m_r(m_r, u)} \\
 & + \beta_{gull}^m \phi_g^{m_l(m_l)} + \beta_{gulr}^m \phi_g^{m_r(m_r)} \\
 & + \gamma_{gull}^m \phi_g^{m_l(m_l(m_l))} + \gamma_{gulr}^m \phi_g^{m_r(m_r(m_r))} \\
 & + \eta_{gull}^m j_{gul}^{+m_l(m_l(m_l))} + \eta_{gulr}^m j_{gur}^{-m_r(m_r(m_r))}
 \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 j_{gur}^{+m} = & \alpha_{0rgu}^m \phi_g^m + \alpha_{gurl}^m \phi_g^{m_l(m_l, u)} + \alpha_{gurr}^m \phi_g^{m_r(m_r, u)} \\
 & + \beta_{gurl}^m \phi_g^{m_l(m_l)} + \beta_{gurr}^m \phi_g^{m_r(m_r)} \\
 & + \gamma_{gurl}^m \phi_g^{m_l(m_l(m_l))} + \gamma_{gurr}^m \phi_g^{m_r(m_r(m_r))} \\
 & + \eta_{gurl}^m j_{gul}^{+m_l(m_l(m_l))} + \eta_{gurr}^m j_{gur}^{-m_r(m_r(m_r))}
 \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

Eqs.(7),(8) provide an explicit NEM-M0-consistent relationship between an outcurrent versus different nodal flux values in different successive neighbors along each axis u , and for each orientation (left, right), plus two (usually relatively small) terms associated with distant incurrents that enter the outermost neighbors. For the different interpolation factors, exact formulae in terms of the known NEM-coefficients c_{igu}^m can be derived. As such, Eqs.(7),(8) represent a fully valid, exact NEM-M0 formulation that offers very convenient properties for the derivation of optimal interpolation weight factors. The latter depend on the node, the energy group, the Cartesian axis, the orientation (left or right) and on the neighbor distance. The determination of their adequate values does not strongly depend on whether or not, for a given collection of intermediately progressed nodal fluxes and interface currents, Eqs.(7),(8) are precisely balanced numerically. This means that, in Eqs.(7),(8), the currents on the left hand side must not necessarily be precisely balanced with those on the right hand side. Such a scenario applies already if the standard nodal diffusion computations are being pursued with use of an analytical nodal diffusion approach (and not with NEM-M0). Nonetheless, Eqs.(7),(8) then do keep the suitability as approximation for the mere purpose of deriving suitable values for the interpolation weight factors. If the nodal fluxes and interface currents are already somewhat converged with reasonable accuracy, Eqs.(7),(8) can be used for determining the appropriate interpolation weight factors. Their purpose is to enable novel preconditioning properties for enhancing the stability and acceleration efficiency of the rebalancing operations. When denoting the right-hand-side terms in Eqs.(7),(8) as Θ_{gul}^{-m} and Θ_{gur}^{+m} , respectively, the interpolation formulae for the (group-dependent) outcurrent driving factors \tilde{d}_{gul}^{-m} and \tilde{d}_{gur}^{+m} , in dependence on the nodal driving factors in the neighboring nodes, can be defined as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{d}_{gul}^{-m} = & \frac{1}{\Theta_{gul}^{-m}} [\\
 & \alpha_{0lgu}^m \phi_g^m d_m \\
 & + \alpha_{gull}^m \phi_g^{m_l} d_{m_l(m)} + \alpha_{gulr}^m \phi_g^{m_r(m)} d_{m_r} \\
 & + \beta_{gull}^m \phi_g^{m_l(m_l)} d_{m_l(m_l)} + \beta_{gulr}^m \phi_g^{m_r(m_r)} d_{m_r(m_r)} \\
 & + \gamma_{gull}^m \phi_g^{m_l(m_l(m_l))} d_{m_l(m_l(m_l))} + \gamma_{gulr}^m \phi_g^{m_r(m_r(m_r))} d_{m_r(m_r(m_r))} \\
 & + \eta_{gull}^m j_{gul}^{+m_l(m_l(m_l))} d_{m_l(m_l(m_l))} + \eta_{gulr}^m j_{gur}^{-m_r(m_r(m_r))} d_{m_r(m_r(m_r))}]
 \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{d}_{gur}^{+m} = & \frac{1}{\Theta_{gur}^{+m}} [\\
 & \alpha_{0rgu}^m \phi_g^m d_m \\
 & + \alpha_{gurl}^m \phi_g^{m_l} d_{m_l(m)} + \alpha_{gurr}^m \phi_g^{m_r(m)} d_{m_r} \\
 & + \beta_{gurl}^m \phi_g^{m_l(m_l)} d_{m_l(m_l)} + \beta_{gurr}^m \phi_g^{m_r(m_r)} d_{m_r(m_r)} \\
 & + \gamma_{gurl}^m \phi_g^{m_l(m_l(m_l))} d_{m_l(m_l(m_l))} + \gamma_{gurr}^m \phi_g^{m_r(m_r(m_r))} d_{m_r(m_r(m_r))} \\
 & + \eta_{gurl}^m j_{gul}^{+m_l(m_l(m_l))} d_{m_l(m_l(m_l))} + \eta_{gurr}^m j_{gur}^{-m_r(m_r(m_r))} d_{m_r(m_r(m_r))}]
 \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

In Eqs.(9),(10), $m_l(m)$ and $m_r(m)$ denote the left and right neighbor of node m (along the concerned axis u), respectively, and so on. Upon inserting these equations into Eq.(2), another transformed finest-mesh rebalancing equation emerges:

$$\left[\tilde{A}_m - \frac{1}{k_{eff}} F_m \right] d_m = \sum_{m'(m)} \tilde{j}_{m \leftarrow m'}^{(1)} d_{m'} + \sum_{m''(m)} \tilde{j}_{m \leftarrow m''}^{(2)} d_{m''} + \sum_{m'''(m)} \tilde{j}_{m \leftarrow m'''}^{(3)} d_{m'''} \quad (11)$$

Eq.(11) includes abstract multi-neighbor coupling operators denoted as $\tilde{j}^{(1)}, \tilde{j}^{(2)}, \tilde{j}^{(3)}$. These are now not merely coarse-mesh-projected interface current values (as in Eq.(3)). Instead, they represent the generalized influential coupling with the more distant (second, third) neighbors along each Cartesian axis (and in each direction: left, right). Nonetheless, the computational advantage of needing to iteratively solve only the nodal driving factors d_m is preserved. Once the d_m are available with high numerical convergence precision, the interface-dependent outcurrent driving factors can be computed directly as interpolation-based by-products of the nodal driving factor array, through execution of Eqs.(9),(10). This obviously means that the driving factors that emerge from the iterative solution of Eq.(11) are different from those determined by Eq.(2). Since Eq.(11) includes the more accurate within-core influential coupling, application of the thereby improved (and numerically different) driving factors can be expected to enforce a clearly more powerful acceleration effect in the overall nodal diffusion iterative solution process. Clearly, Eq.(11) features a somewhat higher dimension. However, it should be noted that, per Cartesian axis u , only two additional terms are added. Accordingly, the rise in iteration cost is a minor penalization that is generously compensated by the enhanced convergence acceleration. It has been verified as well that Eq.(11) can be compressed to a rebalancing form that features the same operator dimensions compared to Eq.(2), while yet preserving the essential convergenc enhancement upgrade. It is noted that, due to the interpolation factors featuring energy group dependence, the prolongation of the nodal interface currents includes not only directional dependence but also energy group dependence:

$$\mathbf{P} : \begin{pmatrix} \phi_g^m \\ j_g^{m' \leftarrow m} \end{pmatrix} \longrightarrow \begin{pmatrix} d_m \phi_g^m \\ \tilde{d}_g^{m' \leftarrow m} j_g^{m' \leftarrow m} \end{pmatrix} \quad \forall g, m, m'(m) \quad (12)$$

The group-dependent interpolation weight factors need to be (re-)computed only periodically during each computation (so not necessarily after each individual nodal diffusion sweep). Accordingly, the cost connected with their acquisition is very low. Since the interpolation weight factors basically follow the core state, they adapt themselves to whatever relevant changes in fuel distribution, burnup, control rod movements, and so on. Accordingly, this interpolation approach can be referred to as *self-adaptive*. Eq.(11) (or its compressed form) can be solved iteratively by use of the prior available rebalancing solver subroutines, which include the application of restarted preconditioned BiCGStab sequences with usage of shift inversion [9]. It is noted that, as part of the overall new approach, the iterative solution process is still started with application of some few rebalancing operations according to Eqs.(2),(3). This secures the initial sufficient intermediate numerical accuracy of the nodal solution, such that adequate interpolation weight factors, needed for the setup of Eq.(11), can be determined. In Figs.3,4, which are commented more extensively in the next section, this is visible in terms of the initial convergence behavior being the same between the compared curves.

4. VERIFICATION OF THE ACHIEVED IMPROVEMENTS

Fig.3 illustrates the kind of acceleration enhancement that is achievable by the introduction of the newly developed self-adaptive interpolation. Clearly, the approach commensurate with Eqs.(11),(12) ("use of interpolation") enables the better acceleration effect, as compared to application of Eq.(4) and no interpolation applied. As illustrated in Fig.4, a further high benefit could be confirmed for some known challenging multi-physics computations pursued with ARTEMIS. Use of the new setup enabled more stable

Figure 3. Comparison of convergence efficiencies between usage versus no usage (of the new self-adaptive interpolation approach (challenging stand-alone flux computation on test core with irregular axial nodal mesh)).

Figure 4. For the concerned challenging non-linear multi-physics iterative solution process, use of the new self-adaptive interpolation approach in the flux solver's CMR mechanism enabled a robust resolution of the prior solution divergence.

behavior, such as in response to non-linear disturbances imposed in the overall non-linear multi-physics iterative solution process. Among other, this features a far better recovery from the above-mentioned non-linear disturbances. In ARTEMIS transient computations, the new setup also enabled substantial improvements in convergence efficiency. Accordingly, this enabled a noticeable improvement in the transient flux solver's CPU run time performance.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Since many years, in the execution of steady-state and transient 3D full-core reactor computations with Framatome's reactor code ARTEMIS, Coarse Mesh Rebalancing has been applied as standardized, mature acceleration mechanism. For enabling a further CMR efficiency upgrade, a novel self-adaptive interpolation approach was developed recently. Through its integration in the automated computation of the relevant restriction and prolongation operators, a transformed rebalancing equation was enabled. The new setup features an improved projection of the influential couplings between the different parts of the reactor core. For the overall multi-group nodal flux iterative solution process (and also for the enveloping multi-physics-coupled solution processes), this has enabled a noticeable further upgrade in CMR efficiency and robustness. In ARTEMIS transient computations, as expected the new setup enabled a noticeable improvement in the transient flux solver's CPU run time performance.

ARCADIA and ARTEMIS are trademarks or registered trademarks of Framatome or its affiliates, in the U.S.A. or other countries.

REFERENCES

- [1] G. Hobson et al., ARTEMIS: The core simulator of AREVA NP's next generation coupled neutronics/thermal-hydraulics code system ARCADIA, *Proceedings PHYSOR 2008*, Interlaken, Switzerland (2008).
- [2] B. Hartmann et al., Validation Results for AREVA NP's Next Generation Core Design System ARCADIA, *Proceedings of the Annual Meeting on Nuclear Technology*, Germany (2010).
- [3] W. Hackbusch, Multi-Grid Methods and Applications, *Springer*, Berlin (1985).
- [4] U. Trottenberg, C. Oosterlee, A. Schüller, Multigrid, *Academic Press* (2001).
- [5] S. Nakamura, Computational Methods in Engineering and Science, *Wiley & Sons* (1977).
- [6] G.R. Cefus, E.W. Larsen, Stability Analysis of Coarse Mesh Rebalancing, *Nuclear Science and Engineering* **105** (1990).
- [7] R. Böer, R. Böhm, H. Finnemann, R. Müller, The Coupled Neutronics and Thermal-Hydraulics Code System PANBOX for PWR Safety Analysis, *Atomenergie/Kerntechnik* **57**, pp.49-54 (1992).
- [8] R.G. Grummer et al., Siemens Integrated Code System CASCADE-3D for Core Design and Safety Analysis, *Proceedings PHYSOR 2000*, Pittsburgh USA, 2000.
- [9] R. van Geemert, Synergies of Acceleration Methodologies for Whole-Core N/TH-Coupled Steady-State and Transient Computations, *Proceedings PHYSOR 2006*, Vancouver, Canada (2006).
- [10] H. Finnemann, F. Bennewitz, M. Wagner, Interface current techniques for multidimensional reactor calculations, *Atomkernenergie (ATKE)* **30** (1977).
- [11] Y.I. Kim, Y.J. Kim, S.J. Kim, T.K. Kim, A semi-analytic multi-group nodal method, *Annals of Nuclear Energy* **26**, pp.699-708 (1999).